

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 883075.

METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D2.2

Data Management Plan

Editor(s):	Pantelis Velanas
Responsible Partner:	European University Cyprus
Status-Version:	Final V2.0
Date:	06/09/2021
Distribution level (PU):	Public

Copyright message

© METICOS Consortium, 2021

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Project Number:	GA 883075
Project Title:	METICOS

Title of Deliverable:	Data Management Plan
Due Date of Delivery to the EC:	28/02/2021

Work package responsible for the Deliverable:	WP1 - Project Management
Editor(s):	Pantelis Velanas (EUC)
Contributor(s):	Giannis Spyropoulos (EUC) Christiana Themistocleous (EUC)
Reviewer(s):	Frank Dumortier (VUB) Raimund Schatz (AIT)
Approved by:	All Partners
Recommended/mandatory readers:	All Partners

Abstract:	This deliverable report provides the data management plan in relation to the data that will be collected and processed.
Keyword List:	Data Management Plan (DMP)
Disclaimer	This deliverable reflects only the author's views and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Document Description

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
V0.1	15/02/2021	First draft version	EUC
V0.2	26/02/2021	Comments and suggestions received by consortium partners	ALL
V1.0	03/03/2021	Final version	EUC
V1.1	24/08/021	Resubmission Draft	EUC
V2.0	06/09/2021	Final Resubmission Version	EUC

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction.....	7
2. Purpose and scope	8
2.1. Data related to the pilot cases	9
2.2. Data related to scientific publications.....	11
3.1. METICOS Public Deliverables.....	12
4. Methodological Framework for Data Management Plan	13
4.1. FAIR.....	13
4.2. Data related to the pilot cases	15
4.3. Data related to scientific publications.....	16
4.4. Data related to deliverables	16
5. Resources, Security and Ethical Aspects	17
5.1. Allocation of resources.....	17
5.2. Data Security and Protection	17
5.3. Ethical Aspects.....	17
6. METICOS Research Datasets	18
7. Data Archiving and Preserving Infrastructure	21
7.1. Project Depository.....	21
7.2. Project Website	21
7.3. Code Repository	21
8. Conclusion	23
Annex I: FAIR Template	24
Annex 2: Datasets and Information	26

Terms and abbreviations

CO	Confidential
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ORD	Open Research Data
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository

Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to present a first version of the plan for the management, collection, generation, storage and preservation of data related to METICOS activities.

Specific/closed proprietary data, if any, will be taken into account with any specific dataset with specific issues regarding openness. During this first version, no data of this kind exists, but if such data is to be taken into account, it will be considered along with its relationship with IPR management and the approach to exploitable results.

Most of this information will be openly accessed and compliant to EC's Horizon 2020 guidelines and Open Data Regulations.

The publishing repositories should be publicly accessible and offer a secure and reliable environment for data storage. Moreover, they should be promoted as much as possible so that they are well known in their respective field in order to fulfil the project dissemination purposes.

Finally, it is important to underline that the current deliverable will be a living document which will be continuously adapted depending on the needs of the project research and development objectives, and based on the direct input from members of the consortium and actual system users.

1. Introduction

This deliverable focuses on the management of data in METICOS and provides for the management, collection, generation, storage and preservation of data related to METICOS activities.

It is important to manage data appropriately in order to comply with security and ethical requirements as well as enhance research integrity and promote the reuse of data.

This deliverable report follows the established H2020 template for a DMP¹.

Section 2 presents a summary of the purpose of the data collection and generation in the case of METICOS.

Section 3 explains how the data and metadata will be made FAIR and thus accessible, findable and reusable.

Section 4 briefly explains how the financial resources are envisioned to be allocated at this stage and focuses on the security and ethical aspects.

Section 5 provides a template of the foreseen datasets for METICOS.

Section 6 describes the platforms and repositories chosen for the METICOS data storage and dissemination.

Section 7 represents the conclusions and future work.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/reporting/h2020-tpl-aa-data-mgt-plan-annotated_en.pdf

2. Purpose and scope

METICOS aims to develop a platform that integrates information systems and networks of data sources in order to validate the efficiency and user's acceptance of border control technologies i.e. fingerprint & iris scanner.

The primary purpose of these technologies is to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of border controls, provide more accurate data on entry and exit systems of the EU, speed up board crossings, to examine the efficiency of the new border technologies, the societal and ethical impact on the travellers, including non-EU citizens, the satisfaction and acceptance of both border authorities/managers and travellers, and ultimately to lead in "no gate crossing point solutions" that allow for the seamless crossing of borders and security checks for the vast majority of travellers.

In this context, every action pertaining data (from collection, generation and processing to distribution, storage and preservation) is examined and determined in the Data Management Plan (DMP), an early version of which is presented in this deliverable. Due to the METICOS social aspect, the management of all these data that will arise throughout the project's lifecycle is crucial for its success. Protecting confidential, personal data or sensitive personal information and complying with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and with relevant national legislations, while at the same time contributing to the open research and innovation, are some of the issues to be addressed.

Emphasis should be given on the protection of personal and sensitive data but also on providing a clear description of the access regimes that will apply to collected datasets.

The proposed plan was designed to allow the efficient dissemination of results and the stimulation of research without jeopardising not meeting any ethical requirements of the project.

METICOS project consortium commits to undertake its research in accordance with the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles as well as in conformity with generally accepted ethical principles for scientific research.

Participants in research should have confidence in the experiments. Good research is possible only if there is a mutual respect and confidence between experimenters and participants. METICOS will avoid situations where participants feel pressured to take part in an experiment, for example, employees or clients. Direct payments are not expected for participation, but other incentive mechanisms may be applied to encourage participation, as well as the adoption of certain behaviours. Such incentive mechanisms will not be designed to provoke excessive competition among participants.

The procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants are described in D1.1, including templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation of humans and data protection issues. In addition, this DMP should be read in conjunction with D1.3 and D1.3 which contains the personal data requirements the METICOS project must comply with as well as a description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to these data.

Therefore, being more of a preliminary and complementary approach, this document is not supposed to answer definitively all requirements set in the H2020 guidelines. On the contrary, it will be regularly updated within the project's lifecycle, whenever significant changes arise (e.g. new data, changes in consortium policies or composition, etc.), in order to lay the foundations for the final DMP release,

which will be presented in final report [M36] and will include all data generated in the course of the 3 years.

2.1. Data related to the pilot cases

The aim of this section is to establish what the purpose is for the collection and generation of data within METICOS pilot cases, which are the sources of this data, if relevant, and how this is important to materialise or achieve the objectives of METICOS.

So, the initial and non-exhaustive list of types and categories of data collected from the pilot cases that will be produced in METICOS is:

- **Personal data:** Article 4 (1) of the GDPR defines personal data as “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”. This definition must be interpreted broadly. Hence, unduly restricting the interpretation of the concept of personal should also be avoided in order to ensure full consistence with EU regulatory requirements. The concept of “personal data” includes not just factual and objective records (name, date of birth, address, occupation, nationality, e-mail address, twitter ID, passport number) but also subjective opinions, intentions and predictions, either correct or incorrect, about individuals, regardless of their position of capacity (as citizen, traveller, employee, customer, , etc.), and regardless of the format or medium on which that information is contained (consortium partners’ servers and computers, users’ mobile devices, audio and video recordings of participants, e-mails to participants, etc). Furthermore, data must be considered “relating” to a certain person as from the moment in can certain way or influence the status or behaviour of an individual (for example by providing a particular user with recommendations). As for the term “identifiable”, the main point about identification of a person is not whether one knows his/her name, but, on the contrary, whether the person can be distinguished from others as recalled by recital 26 of the GDPR which states that “to determine whether a natural person is identifiable, account should be taken of all the means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out”.

Moreover, Article 9 of the GDPR identifies “special categories” of personal data as follows “personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation”. When such “special categories” of personal data are being identified, special attention must be paid.

In the context of METICOS, it should also be recalled that the use of biometric data and in particular facial recognition entail heightened risks for data subjects’ rights. It is crucial that recourse to such technologies takes place with due respect to the principles of lawfulness, necessity, proportionality and data minimisation as set forth in the GDPR. Whereas the use of these technologies can be perceived as particularly effective, controllers should first of all assess the impact on fundamental rights and freedoms and consider less intrusive means to achieve their legitimate purpose of the processing. To qualify as biometric data as defined in the GDPR, processing of raw data, such as the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, must imply a measurement of this characteristics. Since biometric data is the result of such measurements, the

GDPR states in its Article 4.14 that it is “[...] resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person [...]”.

- Such data may be created by the interaction of a person within METICOS and it could come from different sources, such as:
 - Obtrusive data: It requires the direct interaction of the person, either with the infrastructure or with the researchers; the individuals are then aware of the fact that they are being studied, which can influence their responses or behaviour. Some examples of where this data may come from include:
 - Questionnaires – Interviews used for the data collection.
 - Wearable sensors
 - Other infrastructure/IoT devices/sensors
 - Unobtrusive data: it is created indirectly by the person; it does not require an explicit interaction. Subjects are then not aware of the fact that they are being studied. For example, presence or location sensors. In this regard, it should be noted that the European Data Protection Board highlights that, sometimes, such categories of data can be considered as increasing the possible risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals. These personal data are considered as sensitive (as this term is commonly understood) because they are linked to household and private activities (such as electronic communications whose confidentiality should be protected), or because they impact the exercise of a fundamental right (such as location data whose processing questions the freedom of movement). In this context, it is also important to note that electronic identification data such as IP, MAC addresses or alike are considered to be personal data of personal nature. Indeed, such “traffic data” allow very precise conclusions to be drawn concerning the private lives of the persons whose data have been processed, such as everyday habits, permanent or temporary places of residence, daily or other movements, the activities carried out, the social relationships of those persons and the social environments frequented by them. In particular, that data provides the means no less sensitive, having regard to the right to privacy than the actual content of communications. Moreover, collection and retention of pictorial or audio-visual information on all persons entering a monitored space that are identifiable on basis of their looks or other specific elements enables further processing of personal data as to the persons’ presence and behaviour in the given space. In METICOS, it should be avoided that biometric systems would be installed in uncontrolled environments, which means, for example, that no systems should be installed involving capturing on the fly the faces of any individual passing in the range of the camera, including persons who have not consented to the biometric device.
- **Environmental data:** It is created without intervention of a person. Some of the common environmental data types consists of; weather, air quality, and pollen data.
- **Public Data:** It is data already available in public repositories. As regards reuse of public data, the ethical requirement contained in D1.3 requires an explicit confirmation that the public data used in the project can be freely used for the purposes of the project. Indeed, secondary use of public data (whether related or not to the purpose originally assigned to the system) entail risks of misuse. The general principles in GDPR (Article 5), should always be carefully considered.

Pilot cases are a key pillar of METICOS as they will validate the work to be performed in the technological work packages.

2.2. Data related to scientific publications

METICOS will publish scientific publications in conferences and journals as part of the planned dissemination activities. Following the EC Mandate on Open Access, METICOS adheres to the Open Access policy choosing the most appropriate route for each case. Whenever possible, METICOS favours the ‘green’ open access route, in which the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript will be deposited in an online repository, before, at the same time as, or after publication, ensuring that the embargo period requested by certain publishers has elapsed.

Scientific publications data is made available often using accessible PDF files. The metadata to be used will be compliant with the format requested by OpenAIRE as well as the one requested by the repository where the papers are to be deposited.

3.1. METICOS Public Deliverables

All information and material related to the public, such as public deliverables, brochure, posters and so on, will be freely available on the project website. When IPR of foreground knowledge needs to be protected, the corresponding disclosures will be published.

All deliverables include a set of keywords and a brief description that aim to facilitate the indexing and search of the deliverables in search engines. The keywords in each deliverable aim to stress the main topics addressed in the documents.

The audience of the public deliverables of METICOS range from general audiences, interested in activities performed in the project, to more specialised audiences in the different sectors and stakeholders or those who wish to learn about the benefits of METICOS through the experiences gathered through the pilots.

4. Methodological Framework for Data Management Plan

4.1. FAIR

The role of a DMP is to define a framework concerning the handling of research data generated or acquired as the project progresses, but also after the end of it. Subjects for investigation are: the nature of the data in question, which data will be collected and to whom they will be useful, the use of metadata to render data easily retrievable, standardisation, whether and which data will be open-access, how they will be stored and preserved, etc.

Aiming to actively be part of the Open Research Data Pilot, the METICOS project complies with the H2020 guidelines for making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable (FAIR). To achieve that, the FAIR template provided by the European Commission² is followed. This template is mainly a set of questions addressing the four principles and other related issues and can be found in its original form in Annex I of this document.

The components included in FAIR are the following:

- Data Summary;
- FAIR Data Principles;
 - o Making data findable, including provisions for metadata;
 - o Making data openly accessible;
 - o Making data interoperable;
- Increase data re-use (by clarifying licences);
- Allocation of resources;
- Data Security;
- Ethical Aspects;
- Other Issues referring to other national/ funder/ sectorial/ departmental procedures for data management that are used (if any).

The Data Summary and the FAIR Data Principles will be addressed separately for each dataset that is expected to be generated from the METICOS project, in Section 4. In the adapted template, for the sake of readability, all questions under Data Summary and FAIR Data Principles were codified and transformed into a bullet list. This template will be used for all dataset descriptions. In this early stage, it is not required to cover all points exhaustively for each dataset, as this DMP will be updated during the project, whenever new data or other significant changes emerge.

Allocation of resources for storage and archiving is not foreseen, as the selected online storage solutions described below, are available free of charge. As regards publication and other open access costs, they will be provided under the project³.

By default, Horizon 2020 projects participate in the Open Research Data Pilot and they must deposit the following data in a research data repository:

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

³ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/oa-pilot/h2020-hi-erc-oa-guide_en.pdf

1. All data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, including the metadata that describe the research data deposited. This is called the “underlying data”. Such data must be deposited as soon as possible.
2. Any other data (for instance, curated data not directly attributable to a publication, or raw data), including the associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the DMP – that is, according to the individual judgement by each project/grantee.
3. Projects should also provide information via the chosen repository about the tools that are needed to validate the results, e.g., specialised software or software code, algorithms and analysis protocols. Where possible, they should provide these instruments themselves, or alternatively, provide direct access to them.

In the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020⁴, the European Commission states: “Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.”

Researchers, information managers, and other stakeholders can rely on a framework of various international certification standards for digital repositories to assess and improve the quality of their work processes and management systems. “Trustworthy Digital Repository” (TDR) is a term often used in this respect.

Beneficiaries must also provide open access, through the repository, to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. The purpose of the bibliographic metadata requirement is to make it easier to find publications and ensure that EU funding is acknowledged. Information on EU funding must therefore be included as part of bibliographic metadata so that Horizon 2020 can be properly monitored, statistics produced, and the programme's impact assessed.

To monitor any embargo periods, the publication date and embargo period must be provided. The persistent identifier (for example, a Digital Object Identifier) identifies the publication. It enables a link to be provided to an authoritative version of the publication.

Open Access is one of the main principles of Horizon 2020⁵; by Open Access, we refer to the provision of free of charge online access to scientific information for any user. The beneficiaries' obligation to granting open access is differentiated between scientific publications and research data.

- Scientific publication: Publication of academic and research work, most often in the form of an article, research paper and otherwise, in scientific journals or in other forms (e.g. textbook, conference proceedings, etc.).
- Research data: This refers to the recorded factual material commonly accepted in the scientific community as necessary to validate research findings. Examples of research data generated from a project like METICOS could include: Questionnaires, Algorithms, Methodologies, Source Code, etc.

⁵ H2020 Multi-Beneficiary General Model Grant Agreement v5.0, available at: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/mqa/qqa/h2020-mqa-qa-multi_en.pdf

All participating projects' beneficiaries are required to ensure open access for their peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results, as defined in Article 29.2 of the H2020⁶.

4.2. Data related to the pilot cases

Recital 159 of the GDPR states that “the processing of personal data for scientific research purposes should be interpreted in a broad manner including, for example, technological development and demonstration, fundamental research, applied research and privately funded research”. It leaves no doubt that personal data collected and processed in the context of the METICOS pilot cases fall into this definition. Consequently, the members of the METICOS consortium should carefully respect the following principles enshrined in the GDPR. In order to meet the specificities of processing personal data for scientific research purposes in the context of METICOS, specific attention should be drawn to article 89 of the GDPR according to which “processing for [...] scientific research purposes shall be subject to appropriate safeguards [...] for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimization. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner”.

In other words, article 89 of the GDPR recommends “anonymisation” of data processed for research purposes. If this is not feasible, the possibility of “pseudonymisation” of data should be examined. Only if neither anonymisation nor pseudonymisation are possible, “raw” personal data may be used.

The concepts of “anonymisation” and “pseudonymisation” are examined hereunder:

- “Anonymisation” of data means processing it with the aim of irreversibly preventing the identification of the individual to whom it relates. Data can be considered anonymised when it is aggregated⁷ and it does not allow identification of the individuals to whom it relates, and it is not possible that any individual could be identified from the data by any further processing of that data or by processing it together with other information, which is available or likely to be available.
- “Pseudonymisation” of data means replacing any identifying characteristics in the database with a pseudonym, or, in other words, a value, which does not allow the data subject to be directly identified. Pseudonymisation should be distinguished from anonymisation, as it only provides a limited protection for the identity of data subjects because it still allows identification using indirect means. Indeed, where a pseudonym is used, it is possible to identify the data subject by analysing the underlying or related data.

In accordance with this section, when reporting the METICOS pilots in Deliverables, when possible personal data will be anonymized. If not feasible, pseudonymization will be applied. At last resort, when none of these measures can be applied in order to achieve a specific task, “raw” data will be used but under very strict conditions of consent of volunteers and data security requirements.

⁶ H2020 Multi-Beneficiary General Model Grant Agreement v5.0, available at:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/mqa/qqa/h2020-mqa-qa-multi_en.pdf

⁷http://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2014/wp216_en.pdf.

In order to explain the flow of data, how data will be collected and validated, the different sections of the different deliverables related to requirements and pilot scenarios will provide a detailed explanation.

So, at this stage, for all pilot cases, both the collected and generated data, will be anonymized (or pseudonymised in some cases if needed). In any case it not envisioned to be make personal data openly accessible. In any case, all data collected, stored and processed will be treated as strictly confidential, and kept for a specific period of time as it will be stated on a consent form. This time period shall be no longer than necessary to achieve the aims of the scenario and to validate the project objectives and, after this point, the sensitive and personal data will be destroyed as required.

4.3. Data related to scientific publications

The project will favour, whenever possible, the ‘green’ open access route, in which the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript will be deposited in an online repository, before, at the same time as, or after publication, ensuring that the embargo period requested by certain publishers has elapsed.

For the case of the scientific publications, a persistent identification number will be provided when uploading the publications to the selected repository / repositories.

4.4. Data related to deliverables

For the project’s publications on the website, the naming convention to be used will be <<Dx.y Deliverable name _ date in which the deliverable was submitted YYYYMMDD.pdf>>. All deliverables include a set of keywords and a brief description that aim to facilitate the indexing and search of the deliverables in search engines, in accordance to the defined template.

The deliverables will be stored in SharePoint, and for three years beyond the duration time frame of the project. The public deliverables will be accessible through the project website after being accepted by the European Commission.

5. Resources, Security and Ethical Aspects

5.1. Allocation of resources

METICOS does not foresee additional needs for resources beyond the duration of the action to handle data or making the data FAIR. As expressed before, open access repositories will be favoured.

5.2. Data Security and Protection

METICOS will ensure that the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which entered into force in May 2018, is respected, especially in regard to protection of private users' data and also for compliance with national legislations relevant to each of the pilots.

In case of collaboration with border control authorities or other competent authorities resulting in transfers of personal data during pilots, an explicit statement will be asked to these authorities to ensure that such transfers of data are complying with the applicable data protection frameworks.

5.3. Ethical Aspects

The basis of ethical research is the principle of informed consent. This data will be anonymized (or pseudonymised in some case if needed) and reported as aggregated data (when relevant) in the documents related to the evaluation of METICOS outcomes. If participants wish to withdraw from the participation in the pilots at any time, they will be able to do it, and their data, even anonymized data, will be destroyed.

Along with the project other elements will deal with ethical aspects i.e., the setting and operation of the Ethics Board and the ethics management within WP1.

6. METICOS Research Datasets

The current section aims to provide a template for the description of all the foreseen METICOS datasets using the DMP template established by the European Commission for Horizon 2020. The definition of all the related aspects of dataset categories (see Table 1) indicates the importance of long-term preservation of data and the requirement widest possible sharing of the knowledge created by EU projects.

The following template (Table 1) has been developed (in line with the DMP H2020 template requirements) to specifically gather information on the various METICOS datasets.

Table 1 Dataset Management Template

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	A unique and descriptive name for the dataset
Dataset Category	A category the Dataset: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project management data - Primary data collected by partner in METICOS - Secondary data (not publicly available) - Derived data (e.g., output from processing by METICOS module) - Publicly available dataset (e.g. training / benchmark data) - Synthetic / generated data
Partner	The responsible partner for the dataset
Provider (if different from partner)	
Work Package	
Task/Deliverable	If applicable
Details	
Short Description	A short description for the dataset and how it was collected
Existing already before the METICOS project?	YES/NO
Use in METICOS	How the data is/will be used in METICOS
Use beyond METICOS	How the data could be useful to other researchers beyond METICOS
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	Yes – Public; Yes – but restricted access,

	No TBC
Available to METICOS partners?	YES/NO
Access control	How can the data be accessed? (software, techniques, credentials, key pair, etc.)
What kind of processing is involved?	
What kind of derivative data is produced?	
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	
Data flows and views	Describe the data flows and views, i.e. how the data enters the system
How can be managed after the project?	Specify which part of the data can be made publicly available beyond the project end, for which purpose, under which license, and through what kind of infrastructure.
License	Specify license (e.g. Creative commons, Proprietary, etc.)
Type and format	e.g. CSV, TSV, XML, JSON, etc.
Data Size	Can be records, GB, etc.
Storage location	Where will it be stored; (if open, specify repository)
Storing responsible	Who is responsible for storing the data
Secure storage procedures	Which secure storage procedures are used for storing the dataset?
Metadata	Any metadata standards used in the dataset. What metadata has been created and how is this managed
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	Does the dataset contain personal data, and if YES, which? (For details about personal data please see: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/what-personal-data_en) Was informed consent given for use/reuse? Is personal data anonymised?
DPIA required	Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required

Dataset ethics and legal requirements	Please describe any Ethics and/or legal requirements relevant to the dataset - If you want you can refer to relevant Ethics deliverables.
--	---

As at the date of this deliverable, the foreseen datasets and their relevant information are set out in Annex 2.

7. Data Archiving and Preserving Infrastructure

Brief descriptions of the platforms and repositories chosen for the METICOS data storage and dissemination are included in the following section. An outline of their structure and functionalities regarding open access, storage, backup and charging policy is drawn and justifies their selection, as all of them fulfil the requirements elicited from the FAIR data principles and ORD pilot.

7.1. Project Depository

METICOS consortium is using SharePoint provided by Outlook. SharePoint is a tool for storing, managing, and organizing documents. Documents stored in SharePoint are secure, protected from deletion and overwriting and can be tagged with metadata and retention policies allowing users to find the right content at the right time.

METICOS partners use SharePoint as the main document repository of all the files exchanged within the consortium, including intermediate versions of the deliverables, meetings' material (agenda, notes, presentations, demos, minutes, etc.) and any other documents used for gathering inputs from the project's partners. Credentials are needed to access the SharePoint, as the platform usage is restricted only to the METICOS consortium and to the EC (if access is requested).

7.2. Project Website

The METICOS website can be considered as the main online public information point of the project and can be found under this web address: <https://meticos-project.eu/>. The website holds some static text information, such as the brief presentation of key project facts and figures, the rationale and ambition of the latter and the expected impact, while it also offers some dynamic textual data such as the communication of news and events.

There is also a dedicated section (Project Content) outlining the proposed work plan and holding all public data concerning the project and its progress (e.g. public deliverables), as well as a section dedicated to relevant material (Publications and Presentations), encompassing the respective documents using the portable document format (PDF). In case a file is deposited on a social media or data repository platform, a link to the respective source will be provided, enriched with simple metadata information like the title, a short description and the type of the document. The possibility to provide an online discussion forum for practitioners on the scientific and technical fields addressed by METICOS will also be investigated.

All public information on the METICOS website is available with no restrictions and can be accessed by any visitor with no need to create an account or give any personal data. This information and all webpage-related data are backed on a regular basis.

7.3. Code Repository

METICOS software components will be divided into Open and Closed Source components. The classification will be decided on terms which ensure the project's security and protection of partners' business secrets and at the same time reinforce scientific knowledge.

Moving towards this goal, all Open Source Components will be deposited in a public Git based web repository, where they will be at the disposal of the community for exploitation and expansion. Closed Source Components can be stored in private repositories. Git is a distributed version control system and as such, it is promoting sharing and collaboration among users but also offers the creator versioning control.

There are two main options for Git-based hosting providers to consider: GitLab and GitHub.

GitLab⁸ is a Git-based fully integrated software development platform that integrates a great number of essential tools for software development and deployment, and project management:

- Code hosting in repositories with version control;
- Issue Tracker for new implementations, bug reports, and feedback;
- Issue Boards for organisation and prioritisation;
- Code review in Merge Requests with live-preview changes per branch with Review Apps;
- Built-in Continuous Integration, Continuous Deployment, and Continuous Delivery support to build, test, and deploy the application. For each pull or push a CI pipeline is triggered and a group of jobs gets executed in stages (batches). All the jobs in a stage are executed in parallel and if they all succeed the pipeline moves on to the next stage. If one of the jobs fails, the next stage is(usually) not executed. The pipeline usually consists of four stages: build, test, staging, production. The status of the current and historical pipeline is visualised in a specific Pipelines tab to assist the end user in monitoring the deployment process;
- Integration with Docker with GitLab Container Registry. Thus every project can have its own space to store its Docker images.

Apart from GitLab the consortium also considers the option to use GitHub for collaborative software development for open source components.

GitHub⁹ is also a Git-based online repository hosting provider. Although mainly used for code storage, the GitHub platform supports other formats and features too. Being one of the first Git hosting providers, it enjoys a large share of the market, with 24 million connected developers (March 2018). GitHub services are similar to those of GitLab and as such, they also meet the needs of the METICOS project.

Both code repositories provide private repositories. Public and private repositories on GitLab are unlimited, don't have a transfer limit and they include unlimited collaborators. GitHub provides free plans for open-source projects and paid plans offering unlimited private repositories. The final selection between the two repositories will take place as soon as the implementation tasks start.

⁸ <https://about.gitlab.com>

⁹ <https://github.com>

8. Conclusion

The present deliverable report attempts an early approach to the definition of the METICOS DMP. It provides information about the main principles and regulations that the DMP is aligned with and the methodology deriving thereof. Following the EU guidelines regarding open access to scientific publications and research data, and FAIR Data Management, we used consistently the adapted FAIR Data template for presentation of all expected data.

This Deliverable is a first version, and a living document that will be updated during the course of the project accordingly.

Annex I: FAIR Template

DMP component	Issues to be addressed
1. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State the purpose of the data collection/generation • Explain the relation to the objectives of the project • Specify the types and formats of data generated/ collected • Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any) • Specify the origin of the data • State the expected size of the data (if known) • Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful
2. FAIR Data	
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision) • Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers, URL etc.? • Outline naming conventions used • Outline the approach towards search keyword • Outline the approach for clear versioning • Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what type of metadata will be created and how
2.2 Making data openly Accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so • Specify how the data will be made available • Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? • Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited • Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions
2.3. Making data interoperable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability. • Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specify how the data will be licensed to permit the widest reuse possible • Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed • Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why • Describe data quality assurance processes • Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable
3. Allocation of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs • Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project • Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation
4. Data security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data
5. Ethical aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former
6. Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refer to other national/ funder/ sectorial/ departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

Annex 2: Datasets and Information

Table 2 - METICOS_Data_WP11_Newsletters_Content

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	METICOS_Data_WP11_Newsletters_Content
Dataset Category	Publicly available dataset
Partner	ViLabs
Provider (if different from partner)	-
Work Package	WP11
Task/Deliverable	Task 11.1/ D11.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and Material, D11.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation progress report, D11.3, Dissemination, communication and exploitation final progress report
Details	
Short Description	This dataset will comprise the released newsletters for disseminating the activities and the progress made in the METICOS project.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	Mean of disseminating project activities, updates and results
Use beyond METICOS	The developed content will be available for researchers and interested third parties to explore opportunities and public results available via the METICOS project.
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	Yes – Public;
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	The newsletters of the project will be publicly available online right after their official release.
What kind of processing is involved?	An online archive with open access to the released newsletters of the project will be maintained at the relevant webpage of the project website, which is hosted by a VILABS server that is protected by applying the commonly used security measures for preventing unauthorized access and ensuring that security software is up-to-date with the latest released security patches.
What kind of derivative data is produced?	None

How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	The newsletters of the project will be publicly available online right after their official release to the newsletter subscribers and will also be shared on the METICOS Zenodo Repository as well as on the Horizon Results Platform
Data flows and views	-
How can be managed after the project?	All newsletters
License	-
Type and format	PDF files
Data Size	MBs
Storage location	VILABS server
Storing responsible	VILABS
Secure storage procedures	An online archive with open access to the released newsletters of the project will be maintained at the relevant webpage of the project website, which is hosted by a VILABS server that is protected by applying the commonly used security measures for preventing unauthorized access and ensuring that security software is up-to-date with the latest released security patches
Metadata	The newsletters will be prepared and stored in PDF format, while information regarding their release date will be provided. This dataset will be extended whenever new project newsletters are publicly released.
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	NO
DPIA required	Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	All datasets developed or relevant to WP11 follow the Ethical requirements developed by the METICOS Project, as those are defined in the corresponding Deliverables of WP1.

Table 3 - METICOS_Data_WP11_Newsletters_SUBSCRIBERS

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	METICOS_Data_WP11_Newsletters_SUBSCRIBERS
Dataset Category	- Personal Data
Partner	ViLabs
Provider (if different from partner)	Vilabs via the use of MailChimp online tool
Work Package	WP11
Task/Deliverable	Task 11.1/ D11.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and Material, D11.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation progress report, D11.3, Dissemination, communication and exploitation final progress report
Details	
Short Description	An online automated system that provides with an friendly and automated interface for users to subscribe to METICOS Project e-newsletter.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	An online platform to support the secure collection and management of the project newsletter subscribers
Use beyond METICOS	The list of subscribers will not be used afterwards the completion of the METICOS Project
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	NO
Available to METICOS partners?	NO
Access control	Only the individual recognized as the Dissemination Manager of the METICOS Project
What kind of processing is involved?	An online archive with the e-newsletter subscribers, that takes fully into account GDPR and uses the email accounts of the individual who have subscribed to it, only for the purposes of informing them via a newsletter about the project activities. Protected by applying the commonly used security measures for preventing unauthorized access and ensuring that security software is up-to-date with the latest released security patches.
What kind of derivative data is produced?	None

How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	It does not
Data flows and views	-
How can be managed after the project?	It will not
License	-
Type and format	CSV and excel files
Data Size	MBs
Storage location	Mailchimp servers secured with password and two step verification of handler's identity
Storing responsible	VILABS
Secure storage procedures	Mailchimp servers secured with password and two step verification of handler's identity. Consent according all GDPR rules is always collected by the subscribers, while they are provided with the all the corresponding rights: Right of access, right to be forgotten, right to object, right to rectification, and right to portability.
Metadata	Insights and engagement information available only to the application handler.
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	E-mails, and optionally names and surnames
DPIA required	Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	All datasets developed or relevant to WP11 follow the Ethical requirements developed by the METICOS Project, as those are defined in the corresponding Deliverables of WP1.

Table 4 - METICOS_Data_WP11_Scientific Publications

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	METICOS_Data_WP11_Scientific Publications
Dataset Category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Derived data (e.g., output from processing by METICOS module) - Publicly available dataset (e.g. training / benchmark data) - Synthetic / generated data
Partner	ViLabs
Provider (if different from partner)	-
Work Package	WP11, Et al.
Task/Deliverable	Task 11.1/ D11.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and Material, D11.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation progress report, D11.3, Dissemination, communication and exploitation final progress report
Details	
Short Description	This dataset will contain manuscripts reporting the conducted scientific work in METICOS, which have been accepted for publication in peer-reviewed journals and conferences. All these publications will include a statement with acknowledgement to the METICOS project, while their content may vary from the description of specific analysis techniques, to established evaluation datasets and individual components or parts of the METICOS platform.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	The developed content will be available for researchers and interested third parties to explore opportunities and public results as well as knowledge created by the METICOS project.
Use beyond METICOS	The developed content will be available for researchers and interested third parties to explore opportunities and public results as well as knowledge created by the METICOS project.
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	Yes – Public;
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	Self-archiving (also known as "green" open access) will be applied for ensuring open access to these publications. According to this archiving policy the author(s) of the publication will archive

	(deposit) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in online repositories, such as personal webpage(s), the project website and the free-of-charge OpenAIRE or Zenodo repositories, after its publication. Nevertheless, the employed archiving policy will also be fully aligned with restrictions concerning embargo periods that may be defined by the publishers of these publications, making the latter publicly available in certain repositories only after their embargo period has elapsed.
What kind of processing is involved?	An online archive with open access to the released publications of the project will be maintained at the relevant webpage of the project website, which is hosted by a VILABS server that is protected by applying the commonly used security measures for preventing unauthorized access and ensuring that security software is up-to-date with the latest released security patches.
What kind of derivative data is produced?	-
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	This dataset will be publicly available, following the guidelines of the EC for open access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon2020 and will also be shared on the METICOS website, METICOS Zenodo Repository as well as on the Horizon Results Platform
Data flows and views	-
How can be managed after the project?	Self-archiving (also known as "green" open access) will be applied for ensuring open access to these publications. According to this archiving policy the author(s) of the publication will archive (deposit) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in online repositories, such as personal webpage(s), the project website and the free-of-charge OpenAIRE or Zenodo repositories, after its publication. Nevertheless, the employed archiving policy will also be fully aligned with restrictions concerning embargo periods that may be defined by the publishers of these publications, making the latter publicly available in certain repositories only after their embargo period has elapsed.
License	This dataset will be publicly available, following the guidelines of the EC for open access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon2020.
Type and format	PDF files
Data Size	MBs
Storage location	VILABS server
Storing responsible	VILABS
Secure storage procedures	An online archive with open access to the released publications of the project will be maintained at the relevant webpage of the

	project website, which is hosted by a VILABS server that is protected by applying the commonly used security measures for preventing unauthorized access and ensuring that security software is up-to-date with the latest released security patches
Metadata	Most commonly, these documents will be stored in PDF format. Each document will be also accompanied by: (a) details about the venue (e.g. conference, workshop or benchmarking activity) or journal where it was published, (b) a short description with the abstract of the publications, and (c) the related BIB file with its citation. This dataset will be extended whenever new submitted works are accepted for publication in conferences or journals. A simple log file of the performed updates of the dataset will be maintained by VILABS.
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	NO
DPIA required	Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	All datasets developed or relevant to WP11 follow the Ethical requirements developed by the METICOS Project, as those are defined in the corresponding Deliverables of WP1.

Table 5 - METICOS_Data_WP11_Deliverables

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	METICOS_Data_WP11_Deliverables
Dataset Category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publicly available dataset (e.g. training / benchmark data) - Synthetic / generated data
Partner	ViLabs
Provider (if different from partner)	-
Work Package	WP11, et all
Task/Deliverable	Task 11.1/ D11.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and Material, D11.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation progress report, D11.3, Dissemination, communication and exploitation final progress report
Details	
Short Description	This dataset will be composed of the project deliverables that have to be prepared and submitted to the EC during the project's lifespan, according to the contractual obligations of the METICOS consortium.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	Scientific and as KPIs and dissemination and exploitation actions control points
Use beyond METICOS	The developed content will be available for researchers and interested third parties to explore opportunities and public results as well as knowledge created by the METICOS project.
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	Yes – Public;
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	Self-archiving (also known as "green" open access) will be applied for ensuring open access to these publications. According to this archiving policy the author(s) of the publication will archive (deposit) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in online repositories, such as personal webpage(s), the project website and the free-of-charge OpenAIRE or Zenodo repositories, after its publication. Nevertheless, the employed archiving policy will also be fully aligned with restrictions concerning embargo periods that may be defined by the publishers of these publications, making the latter publicly

	available in certain repositories only after their embargo period has elapsed.
What kind of processing is involved?	An online archive with open access to the released Deliverables of the project will be maintained at the relevant webpage of the project website, which is hosted by a VILABS server that is protected by applying the commonly used security measures for preventing unauthorized access and ensuring that security software is up-to-date with the latest released security patches.
What kind of derivative data is produced?	-
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	This dataset will be publicly available, following the guidelines of the EC for open access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon2020 and will also be shared on the METICOS website, METICOS Zenodo Repository as well as on the Horizon Results Platform
Data flows and views	-
How can be managed after the project?	Available on all relevant repositories
License	This dataset will be publicly available, following the guidelines of the EC for open access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon2020.
Type and format	PDF files
Data Size	MBs
Storage location	VILABS server
Storing responsible	VILABS
Secure storage procedures	An online archive with open access to the released Deliverables of the project will be maintained at the relevant webpage of the project website, which is hosted by a VILABS server that is protected by applying the commonly used security measures for preventing unauthorized access and ensuring that security software is up-to-date with the latest released security patches
Metadata	These documents will be stored in PDF format. For each deliverable we will provide: (a) the list of authors, (b) a brief description of its content (i.e. its abstract), (c) the related WP of the project, and (d) the contractual date for their submission to the EC. This dataset will be extended whenever new deliverables are submitted to the EC. A simple log file of the performed updates of the dataset will be maintained by VILABS in the project webpage (hosted by a VILABS server).
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	NO

DPIA required	Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	All datasets developed or relevant to WP11 follow the Ethical requirements developed by the METICOS Project, as those are defined in the corresponding Deliverables of WP1.

Table 6 - METICOS_Data_WP11_Presentations

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	METICOS_Data_WP11_Presentations
Dataset Category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publicly available dataset (e.g. training / benchmark data) - Synthetic / generated data
Partner	ViLabs
Provider (if different from partner)	-
Work Package	WP11, et all
Task/Deliverable	Task 11.1/ D11.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and Material, D11.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation progress report, D11.3, Dissemination, communication and exploitation final progress report
Details	
Short Description	This dataset will consist of presentations prepared for reporting METICOS-related scientific work or progress made, in a variety of different events, such as conferences, workshops, meetings, exhibitions, interviews and so on.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	Presentation of METICOS progress and achievements
Use beyond METICOS	The developed content will be available for researchers and interested third parties to explore opportunities and public results as well as knowledge created by the METICOS project.
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	Yes – Public;
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	According to the type of events and the type of information included in the presentation.
What kind of processing is involved?	The project presentations will be publicly available for view and download via the relevant the relevant webpage of the project website, which is hosted by a VILABS server that is protected by applying the commonly used security measures for preventing unauthorized access and ensuring that security software is up-to-date with the latest released security patches

What kind of derivative data is produced?	-
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	This dataset will be publicly available, following the guidelines of the EC for open access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon2020 and will also be shared on the METICOS website, METICOS Zenodo Repository as well as on the Horizon Results Platform
Data flows and views	-
How can be managed after the project?	Available on all relevant repositories
License	This dataset will be publicly available, following the guidelines of the EC for open access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon2020.
Type and format	PDF files
Data Size	MBs
Storage location	VILABS server
Storing responsible	VILABS
Secure storage procedures	The project presentations will be publicly available for view and download via the relevant the relevant webpage of the project website, which is hosted by a VILABS server that is protected by applying the commonly used security measures for preventing unauthorized access and ensuring that security software is up-to-date with the latest released security patches
Metadata	Most commonly these presentations will be in PPT or PDF format. Information related to: (a) the authors, (b) the presenter, (c) the venue and (d) the date of the presentation will be also stored in plain text. This dataset will be extended whenever new METICOS presentations are prepared and publicly released. A simple log file of the performed updates of the dataset will be maintained by VILABS.
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	NO
DPIA required	Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	All datasets developed or relevant to WP11 follow the Ethical requirements developed by the METICOS Project, as those are defined in the corresponding Deliverables of WP1.

Table 7 - Travellers application - user acceptance Dataset

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	Travellers application - user acceptance Dataset
Dataset Category	Primary data collected by partner in METICOS
Partner	JOAFG
Provider (if different from partner)	JOAFG
Work Package	WP10
Task/Deliverable	T10.3
Details	
Short Description	User acceptance data, collected during pilots and workshops.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	The data will be used for defining an acceptance model. Therefore findings will guide development efforts, help to refine meticos results and ensure that they are useable by end users.
Use beyond METICOS	Not used beyond Meticos
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	TBC
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	directly requested at JOAFG
What kind of processing is involved?	Systematic qualitative and quantitative content analysis
What kind of derivative data is produced?	Acceptance level of no-gate boarder procedures
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	Processed data will be published in journals.
Data flows and views	Pilots questionnaire and interviews/workshops -> transcription -> analysis -> evaluation -> output to deliverable -> output to journal
How can be managed after the project?	Publications provide processed data for public
License	n.a.

Type and format	TBC
Data Size	TBC
Storage location	Radcloud.johanniter.at, project repository
Storing responsible	JOAFG, University Cypres
Secure storage procedures	https://
Metadata	n.a.
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	At this stage: no. can be different when evaluation concept is ready Was informed consent given for use/reuse? -> given Is personal data anonymised? -> yes
DPIA required	Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required -> No. Not until now.
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	At this stage: None. TBC

Table 8 - Middleware input datasets

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	Middleware input datasets
Dataset Category	Primary data collected by partner in METICOS
Partner	MAGG
Provider (if different from partner)	ICSS -METICOS Big Data (dataset) MAGG – Smart Front End (dataset) - BMIS - LEIS - METICOS Ecosystem
Work Package	WP8
Task/Deliverable	T8.2
Details	
Short Description	Various datasets that are being input to the middleware component by other components
Existing already before the METICOS project?	YES (concerning BMIS & LEIS) NO (about new METICOS data)
Use in METICOS	METICOS middleware will be a software system that will facilitate data communication between components and other systems
Use beyond METICOS	TBD
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	NO
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	Authentication needed
What kind of processing is involved?	Aggregation, Encryption, Filtering, Fusion, Transmission
What kind of derivative data is produced?	TBD
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	TBD
Data flows and views	The data enters the system using the Middleware component API.
How can be managed after the project?	TBD

License	TBD
Type and format	TBD
Data Size	N/A
Storage location	TBD
Storing responsible	TBD
Secure storage procedures	Encryption
Metadata	TBD
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	YES
DPIA required	Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	Please describe any Ethics and/or legal requirements relevant to the dataset - If you want you can refer to relevant Ethics deliverables.

Table 9 - Passenger Opinions and Reactions

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	Passenger Opinions and Reactions
Dataset Category	Primary data collected by partner in METICOS
Partner	MAGG
Provider (if different from partner)	MAGG
Work Package	WP8
Task/Deliverable	T8.5
Details	
Short Description	The dataset includes passenger opinions and reactions to the technology used at border checkpoints. It will be collected when the passengers answer questionnaires or use various forms of reactions (smileys).
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	To assess the traveller's opinions on the technology used at border checkpoints; the social acceptance; to enhance the trust to Smart Border solutions by civilians from different cultures.
Use beyond METICOS	The dataset could be useful for researchers to assess the opinions on "intrusive" technology in a more general manner.
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	TBD
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	Authentication needed
What kind of processing is involved?	Encryption
What kind of derivative data is produced?	Analytics of usefulness to METICOS Smart Front End
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	TBD
Data flows and views	The data enters the system by the passengers' interaction with the front end.
How can be managed after the project?	TBD

License	TBD
Type and format	JSON
Data Size	N/A
Storage location	METICOS Big Data Platform
Storing responsible	METICOS Big Data Platform (SIMAVI)
Secure storage procedures	TBD
Metadata	TBD
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	The data is anonymised
DPIA required	Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	Please describe any Ethics and/or legal requirements relevant to the dataset - If you want you can refer to relevant Ethics deliverables.

Table 10 - Sensors dataset

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	Sensors dataset
Dataset Category	Raw data collected by sensors in METICOS
Partner	MAGG
Provider (if different from partner)	END USERS
Work Package	WP8
Task/Deliverable	T8.5
Details	
Short Description	The dataset includes raw data incomings from installed sensors (e.g.1-camera, 2-GPS, TBD) at the airport facilities. The dataset will be collected when the passengers interact with METICOS Smart Front End at the control points (kiosks).
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	Data collection for border control authorities
Use beyond METICOS	The dataset could be useful for LEAS to ensure travel safety and human control entrance to EU.
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	NO
Available to METICOS partners?	NO
Access control	Authentication needed via travel ticket
What kind of processing is involved?	Data encryption
What kind of derivative data is produced?	Contextual Data, Geolocation Data
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	Through Border Management Information systems and Law Enforcement Information Systems
Data flows and views	The data enters the system by the passengers' interaction with the front end at kiosks
How can be managed after the project?	TBD
License	TBD

Type and format	RAW DATA, FORMAT TBD
Data Size	N/A
Storage location	Border Management Information systems and Law Enforcement Information Systems
Storing responsible	LEAs border control authorities
Secure storage procedures	Encryption
Metadata	Under LEAS standards
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	YES
DPIA required	Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	Compliant with EU regulations

Table 11- TAM-STUDY-MOD-01

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	TAM-STUDY-MOD-01
Dataset Category	Primary data collected by partner in METICOS
Partner	AIT
Provider (if different from partner)	
Work Package	WP5
Task/Deliverable	T5.3, D5.3
Details	
Short Description	This dataset is necessary for the probabilistic modelling of stakeholder acceptance of smart border control technologies. It consists of the anonymized results data generated from three online questionnaires studies conducted in the context of T5.2. Two of these studies target citizens from different representative EU countries (to address cultural influence factors) and one survey targets border control staff. The surveys address respondent's awareness, opinions, expectations and likely acceptance of smart border control technologies in the form of quantitative scores.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	The data will be used for training and validating the different technology acceptance models (TAMs) developed in T5.4.
Use beyond METICOS	If made available, external parties could use the data to a) develop their own acceptance models, b) benchmark different smart border technologies w.r.t. acceptance, c) pool the data with results from complementary user studies.
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	No (currently marked as confidential)
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	The data will reside in a password-protected relational database only accessible to project partners.
What kind of processing is involved?	Anonymization (performed by the agency executing the data collection).
What kind of derivative data is produced?	N.A.

How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	N.A.
Data flows and views	The different online surveys will generate the raw data from questionnaire responses
How can be managed after the project?	If made public, the dataset could be provided by the infrastructure of the Open Science Foundation (OSF).
License	Creative Commons BY-NC-SA If made publicly available, this license lets others remix, adapt, and build upon your work non-commercially, as long as they credit METICOS and license their new creations under the identical terms.
Type and format	Relational Tables.
Data Size	< 100 MB
Storage location	A relational database hosted by one of the project partners (default: AIT).
Storing responsible	AIT
Secure storage procedures	Depends on database technology chosen.
Metadata	N.A.
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	The data records collected via online questionnaires will be rendered anonymous in such a way that the individual is not or no longer identifiable, i.e., the anonymisation will be irreversible. Hence, the dataset will not contain personal data.
DPIA required	NO
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	Not necessary

Table 22 - Universal Connector Datasets

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	Universal Connector Datasets
Dataset Category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary data collected by partner in METICOS - Secondary data (not publicly available) - Derived data (e.g., output from processing by METICOS module)
Partner	SIMAVI
Provider (if different from partner)	METICOS Ecosystem BPC
Work Package	WP8
Task/Deliverable	
Details	
Short Description	UC is an intermediate between heterogenous datasources and consumers.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	for METICOS Ecosystem - NO for BPC datasources - YES
Use in METICOS	The component acts as an intermediary between producers and consumers of data. How the datasets are used in METICOS is dataset specific and is described in the corresponding template.
Use beyond METICOS	The component acts as an intermediary between producers and consumers of data. How the datasets are used beyond METICOS is dataset specific and is described in the corresponding template.
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	dataset specific
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	N/A (the data is not stored by this component)
What kind of processing is involved?	The data may be transformed in order to respect a format expected by the consumer component.
What kind of derivative data is produced?	N/A
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	N/A
Data flows and views	The component acts as an intermediary between producers and consumers of data.

How can be managed after the project?	N/A
License	N/A
Type and format	TBD
Data Size	TBD
Storage location	Datasource specific
Storing responsible	Datasource specific
Secure storage procedures	Datasource specific
Metadata	Datasource specific
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	Datasource specific
DPIA required	Datasource specific
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	Datasource specific

Table 13- HDF dataset

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	HDF dataset
Dataset Category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary data collected by partner in METICOS - Secondary data (not publicly available) - Derived data (e.g., output from processing by METICOS module) - Publicly available dataset (e.g. training / benchmark data) - Synthetic / generated data
Partner	SIMAVI
Provider (if different from partner)	METICOS Ecosystem
Work Package	WP4, WP9
Task/Deliverable	
Details	
Short Description	Static / real-time data, structure / unstructured data from heterogenous datasources
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	The data is stored in HDF. The data is organized using hierarchical data models, which will facilitate the data minimization procedure and the scalable hierarchical analysis approach that will be followed by the existing partners' analytics infrastructure (Section 1.3.1) for application on Big Data.
Use beyond METICOS	TBD
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	TBD
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	Authentication needed
What kind of processing is involved?	Data is converted to an hierarchical data model, adapted to METICOS data types.
What kind of derivative data is produced?	TBD
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	TBD

Data flows and views	Data is collected by METICOS components, it is transformed to HDF and persisted.
How can be managed after the project?	TBD
License	N/A
Type and format	HDF
Data Size	TBD
Storage location	CDME component
Storing responsible	SIMAVI
Secure storage procedures	TBD
Metadata	TBD
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	TBD
DPIA required	TBD
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	TBD

Table 34- Social Media Dataset

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	Social Media Dataset
Dataset Category	Publicly available dataset
Partner	ICCS
Provider (if different from partner)	NA
Work Package	WP7 will use this dataset.
Task/Deliverable	Specifically, this dataset will be used in D7.3.
Details	
Short Description	Data from Twitter stream as well as other publicly available datasets (reviews, blogs, Google reviews...) will be crawled from the web in order to derive the social acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies. A Python script is going to be used in order to gather social media data.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	The data will be gathered, stored, cleaned, processed and then submitted to the Advanced Data Analytics Engine, where different machine learning and deep learning algorithms will be applied to them, in order to derive the social impact and acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.
Use beyond METICOS	To be defined
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	NO. Based on Twitter's Terms and Conditions, at the moment we cannot publish this data.
Available to METICOS partners?	NO
Access control	NA
What kind of processing is involved?	The following steps are followed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data gathering • Data pre-processing and cleaning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tokenization ○ Removing unnecessary punctuation, tags ○ Removing stop words ○ Stemming ○ Lemmatization • Feature Extraction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ TFIDF ○ Bag of Words ○ Doc2Vec method

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Choosing and applying Machine Learning Algorithms <p>Then, depending on the algorithm, we can derive clusters-topics of words, sentiment analysis, polarity score, context in which most important words are used and much more.</p> <p>Finally, the visualisation step will illustrate the results of the application of the ML algorithms and will make it accessible to the users of the DTVA METICOS component.</p>
What kind of derivative data is produced?	After the data is gathered, the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data component of METICOS will perform sentiment and context analysis from this data. The user of the Dashboard (DTVA component) will be able to see the most important words, the context where these are used, clusters of the main subjects that people are tweeting about regarding Smart Border Control technologies, sentiment and polarity scores and more.
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	NA
Data flows and views	Along with other sources of data, this dataset, after being crawled and stored, will enter METICOS infrastructure through the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data component. The relevant output will be then forwarded to the Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analytics component for further analysis. Finally, the output will be available through the DTVA component.
How can be managed after the project?	NA
License	NA
Type and format	NA
Data Size	NA
Storage location	TBD
Storing responsible	ICCS
Secure storage procedures	TBD
Metadata	TBD
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	YES
DPIA required	NO
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	Specificly for Twitter, there is the code of conduct established, which outlines the expectations for participant behaviour as well as the consequences of unacceptable behaviour. The link to the

	Twitter Developer Community code of conduct is here → https://developer.twitter.com/en/community/code-of-conduct
--	--

Table 45- T3.2 and T3.3 Workshops

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	T3.2 and T3.3 Workshops
Dataset Category	A category the Dataset: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project management data - Primary data collected by partner in METICOS - Publicly available dataset (e.g. training / benchmark data) - Synthetic / generated data
Partner	VUB
Provider (if different from partner)	METICOS partners and external stakeholders (e.g., technical experts, lawyers, civil servants, privacy advocates, citizens, human rights experts, LEAs, immigration experts, as well as others)
Work Package	WP3
Task/Deliverable	T3.2 and T3.3
Details	
Short Description	We will organize workshops with project partners and external stakeholders for consultation/validation purposes. We will process their e-mails for communication purposes and collect their comments. Their comments will be anonymized when included in the METICOS Deliverables, except if express consent is obtained for non-anonymous publication.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	Produce reports in T3.2 and T3.3 with findings and recommendations.
Use beyond METICOS	Other researchers beyond METICOS could use the data when performing research on ethical and legal issues related to border control technologies.
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	Yes – Public
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	E-mails and comments of internal/external stakeholders will be securely processed exclusively on the researchers' computers and on the University's cloud system with an access control mechanism and strong password strength.
What kind of processing is involved?	Processing of e-mails/comments of internal /external stakeholders.

What kind of derivative data is produced?	Anonymized comments of internal /external stakeholders, except if express consent is obtained for non-anonymous publication.
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	The Deliverables of T3.2 and T3.3 will publicly available on the METICOS website
Data flows and views	Comments will be collected during workshops and anonymized by VUB researchers, except if express consent is obtained for non-anonymous publication.
How can be managed after the project?	The Deliverables of T3.2 and T3.3 will be publicly available on the METICOS website. All non-anonymized comments will be deleted once the deliverables are compiled, except if express consent is obtained for non-anonymous publication.
License	Creative commons
Type and format	Text
Data Size	Not know yet
Storage location	Researchers' computers and university cloud system.
Storing responsible	VUB
Secure storage procedures	No dataset will be produced.
Metadata	N/A
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	<p>The T3.2 and T3.3 Deliverables will contain anonymized comments of internal/external stakeholders, except if express consent is obtained for non-anonymous publication.</p> <p>Was informed consent given for use/reuse? YES Is personal data anonymised? YES, except if express consent if obtained for publication of non-anonymous data.</p>
DPIA required	NO Data Privacy Impact Assessment Required
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	The processing of e-mails and comments in T3.2 and T3.3 will respect the requirements of D1.1 (information sheet and express consent), D1.3 (personal data requirements), D1.4 (security requirements).

Table 16- Unstructured Dataset from METICOS Application and Tablet

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	Unstructured Dataset from METICOS Application and Tablet
Dataset Category	Primary data collected by partner in METICOS
Partner	Pilot partners
Provider (if different from partner)	-
Work Package	WP7 will use this dataset.
Task/Deliverable	Specifically, this dataset will be used in D7.3
Details	
Short Description	The Unstructured Dataset will be gathered through the METICOS mobile application and the METICOS tablet application during the METICOS pilots. This dataset will comprise mostly of responses to free-text questions relevant to the Technology Acceptance of Smart Border Control Technology, generally and specific for the Border Control Point where the traveller is participating in the pilot. Please note that the aforementioned data could be derived from hard copy questionnaires.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	The data will be gathered, stored, cleaned, processed and then submitted to the Advanced Data Analytics Engine for Unstructured Data, where different machine learning algorithms will be applied, in order to derive the social impact and acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.
Use beyond METICOS	To be decided by the data providers
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	To be decided by the data providers
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	This data will be accessed through the METICOS application and tablet.
What kind of processing is involved?	Since this unstructured data is in the form of text, the following steps are followed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data gathering • Data pre-processing and cleaning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tokenization ○ Removing unnecessary punctuation, tags ○ Removing stop words ○ Stemming ○ Lemmatization

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feature Extraction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ TFIDF ○ Bag of Words ○ Doc2Vec method • Choosing and applying Machine Learning Algorithms <p>Then, depending on the algorithm, we can derive clusters-topics of words, sentiment analysis, polarity score, context in which most important words are used and much more.</p> <p>Finally, the visualisation step will illustrate the results of the application of the ML algorithms and will make it accessible to the users of the DTVA METICOS component.</p>
What kind of derivative data is produced?	<p>After the data is gathered, the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data component of METICOS will perform sentiment and context analysis from this data. The user of the Dashboard (DTVA component) will be able to see the most important words, the context where these are used, clusters of the main subjects that the travellers participating in METICOS pilot are writing about for the individual Border Control Point, sentiment and polarity scores and more. Moreover, this dataset will be analysed individually in a standalone manner, but also together with the relevant structured data in order to derive useful correlations of different data attributes (e.g. age with polarity score of the text, sentiment analysis of reviews vs time to cross the border using SBC technologies and many more).</p>
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	To be decided by the data providers
Data flows and views	<p>Along with other sources of data, this dataset, after being crawled and stored, will enter METICOS infrastructure through the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data component. The relevant output will be then forwarded to the Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analytics component for further analysis.</p>
How can be managed after the project?	To be decided by the data providers and METICOS platform integrators
License	TBD
Type and format	TBD
Data Size	NA
Storage location	TBD
Storing responsible	T9.2 Data Hosting - SIMAVI
Secure storage procedures	TBD
Metadata	TBD
Ethics and Data Protection	

<p>Dataset contains personal data?</p>	<p>Personal data is anonymised and there will be no way of mapping the data given from the individual persons to their personal data (name, surname, address etc). Moreover, the travellers will be asked to fill in a consent form prior to taking part in the METICOS pilots. Last but not least, we should note that only adults are allowed to participate in the METICOS pilot use case executions.</p>
<p>DPIA required</p>	<p>The requirement regarding DPIA should be defined in the context of WP3.</p>
<p>Dataset ethics and legal requirements</p>	<p>All the dataset in the context of METICOS should comply with the work conducted as well as the deliverables of WP3.</p>

Table 17- Structured Dataset from METICOS Application and Tablet

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	Structured Dataset from METICOS Application and Tablet
Dataset Category	Primary data collected by partner in METICOS
Partner	<i>Pilot partners</i>
Provider (if different from partner)	-
Work Package	WP7 will use this dataset.
Task/Deliverable	Specifically, this dataset will be used in D7.4.
Details	
Short Description	The Structured Dataset will be gathered through the METICOS mobile application and the METICOS tablet application, and will comprise of various data including but not limited to: Demographics of travellers, responses to questions (as structured data, for example Likert scale, multiple choice, selection boxes...), smileys, quality of service data (including time to cross the border) and others. Please note that several of the aforementioned data could be derived from hard copy questionnaires, where in the first part there would be a demographics section and the rest will comprise of relevant to the Technology Acceptance of Smart Border Control Technology, questions.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	NO
Use in METICOS	The data will be gathered, stored, cleaned and then submitted to the Advanced Data Analytics Engine for Structured Data, where different machine learning algorithms will be applied, in order to derive the social impact and acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.
Use beyond METICOS	To be decided by the data providers
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	To be decided by the data providers
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	This data will be accessed through the METICOS application and tablet.
What kind of processing is involved?	The following steps are to be used: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data gathering - Data pre-processing and cleaning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Identification of outliers o Feature scaling/Normalization

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statistical analysis - Calculation of correlations between attributes of the data - The visualisation step will illustrate the output of the processing (correlations, results from analysis, outlier detection and more) and will make it accessible to the users of the DTVA METICOS component.
What kind of derivative data is produced?	After the data is gathered, the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data component of METICOS will uncover hidden patterns amongst attributes of gathered structured data, regarding technology acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies. The user will be able to see these correlations between different attributes of the data with 2d heatmaps, frequency distributions, time series representation of the data in dynamic scale, ranking of categorical variables, outlier/anomaly detection etc. via the DTVA component (developed in task T9.3). Some examples include the impact of waiting time, demographics, and others on the acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	To be decided by the data providers
Data flows and views	Along with other sources of data, this dataset, after being crawled and stored, will enter METICOS infrastructure through the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data component. The relevant output will be then forwarded to the Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analytics component for further analysis. Finally, the output will be available through the DTVA component.
How can be managed after the project?	To be decided by the data providers and METICOS platform integrators
License	TBD
Type and format	TBD
Data Size	NA
Storage location	TBD
Storing responsible	T9.2 Data Hosting - SIMAVI
Secure storage procedures	TBD
Metadata	TBD
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	Yes. However, the travellers will be asked to fill in a consent form prior to taking part in the METICOS pilots. Last but not least, we

	should note that only adults are allowed to participate in the METICOS pilot use case executions.
DPIA required	The requirement regarding DPIA should be defined in the context of WP3.
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	All the dataset in the context of METICOS should comply with the work conducted as well as the deliverables of WP3.

Table 18- Social toolkit dataset

Template Field	Description
Overview	
Dataset Name	Social toolkit dataset
Dataset Category	It will be a bit of all the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary data collected by partner in METICOS - Secondary data (not publicly available) - Derived data (e.g., output from processing by METICOS module) - Publicly available dataset (e.g. training / benchmark data) - Synthetic / generated data
Partner	NTNU
Provider (if different from partner)	
Work Package	WP6
Task/Deliverable	T6.1-T6.3, D6.1-6.3
Details	
Short Description	The social toolkit dataset will collect data from several sources, including other partner institutions and end users (border control authorities). The data will be generated from the different tasks and activities of the project, but there will also be data types generated in order to help validate existing data collected from the real-life sources.
Existing already before the METICOS project?	No
Use in METICOS	The data will be mainly used to design and implement the social toolkit, trying to map the behaviour of travellers, border authorities and technologies as related to the final decision of border crossing process.
Use beyond METICOS	The dataset might be used in the process of publishing relevant scientific research around the topic of using simulation to map use of technology in border control points.
Storage and access details	
Is the data open?	TBD
Available to METICOS partners?	YES
Access control	The data might be accessed with proper credentials
What kind of processing is involved?	TBD

What kind of derivative data is produced?	TBD
How it becomes accessible to stakeholders outside the consortium?	It might be available through visualizations in specific devices, i.e., dashboards etc.
Data flows and views	The data will be fed into the dataset from multiple sources, updated regularly based on the source and frequency required, and will be further available for the other tasks and activities, according the project objectives
How can be managed after the project?	Main purpose will be related to research and development
License	TBD
Type and format	TBD
Data Size	TBD
Storage location	Social toolkit infrastructure
Storing responsible	NTNU
Secure storage procedures	TBD
Metadata	TBD
Ethics and Data Protection	
Dataset contains personal data?	Yes, anonymised
DPIA required	TBD
Dataset ethics and legal requirements	TBD